

945358-BIGPICTURE
Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP2 - Infrastructure and database hosting

D2.07 - Report on private execution model implementation in operational environment

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Document History

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Abstract

This report describes the functionalities that have been put in place in the operational system to enable execution of potentially untrusted and confidential code on potentially sensitive data, without disclosing information from either. The system was established and operational M10, and has been iteratively improved by wp2 ever since, based on needs identified by the project (wp3-6) and according to project priorities (wp1) within available time and resources (wp2). This is a follow-up to a similar report made during T2.5 – Pilot operation (D2.03 - Report on private execution model implementation in pilot environment, M18), for the purpose of describing findings from this iterative improvement work. This report focuses on technical aspects, while user experience related findings are preferably reported in the contemporaneous report D2.08 - Report on status of operational services implementation.

Despite being originally intended for supporting genetics research specifically, the ELIXIR technologies that the Bigpicture repository infrastructure is building upon have proven to be quite generically capable, and have been received uniformly positive feedback from the digital pathology users of the Bigpicture repository services during the first years of the project. In fact, very little in terms of negative feedback or even feature development requests have arisen.

From this, we conclude that the platform is highly suited to meet needs in digital pathology, at least among those highly technologically advanced users that have pioneered use of the Bigpicture repository infrastructure services (DECI, MUW, RUMC, RÖ, UMCU). However, as the project moves to more advanced usage patterns and opens up to broader ranges of user organisation which may not have access to the same degree of technological expertise as our pioneers, we do anticipate that the needs for feature development could rise, for example implementing further usability features for less tech-savvy users.

Contents

Methods.....	3
Cytomine-server-as-a-service.....	3
SD-Desktop.....	3
grand-challenge.org.....	4
On-demand AI inference on Archive data.....	4
Security review.....	4
Results.....	5
Concepts.....	5
Privacy parameters of the private inference execution model.....	5
Services.....	6
Cytomine.....	6
SD Desktop.....	8
grand-challenge.org.....	8
Security review.....	8
Conclusion.....	9

Methods

This section describes the process under which the results were produced. The results themselves are preferentially described in the [Results](#) section.

The system was operational M10, as reported in D2.2 - Report on the pilot system establishment, and has been iteratively improved ever since, in tasks T2.6 - Iterative development and T2.7 - Regular security review, both of which will be ongoing throughout the remainder of the project. Iterative improvement has been carried out as per Description of the Action (DoA), meaning the platform services originally developed by ELIXIR for facilitating genetics research are operated and continuously adapted to needs in digital pathology research, based on feature requests from the rest of the project (wp3-6, data contribution and use, legal and sustainability aspects) according to project priorities (wp1) and within available time and resources (wp2).

Status of private execution model implementation at M18 (in the heart of T2.5 – Pilot operation, M10-M24) was reported in D2.3 - Report on private execution model implementation in pilot environment. This report is a follow-up timed at M30 (six months into T2.8 – Large scale archive operations, M25-M72) and focuses on results produced in T2.6 and T2.7 since the D2.3 report in M18.

The work methodology and organisation in terms of decision making and requirement dialogue for wp2 service development is described in report D2.08 - Report on status of operational services implementation. As described in D2.08, the platform services have received uniformly positive feedback from current users, and very little in terms of negative feedback or even feature development requests, from which we conclude that the platform services are highly well suited at least to the needs of those technologically advanced digital pathology users that have pioneered use of the Bigpicture repository infrastructure services (DECI, MUW, RUMC, RÖ, UMCU). However, we do anticipate that as wp3 and wp4 start taking steps to address more advanced usage patterns, such as indirect access to datasets and AI algorithms, further needs for development will be identified. Likewise, we anticipate that with the adoption of the Bigpicture legal framework for data sharing that is currently being developed by wp5, it will become possible to open up use of the platform for a wider range of organisations, with a wider range of technological advancement, which could present challenges that it hitherto has simply not been possible to identify in the current use of platform services. Thus, while current users seem happy with the services as they are, we do anticipate that the needs for feature development could rise. WP2 is engaging in this requirement dialogue as described in D2.08 - Report on status of operational services implementation.

Cytomine-server-as-a-service

A model exists for providing Cytomine as a service, as described in the [Cytomine](#) section in Results below. At the same time, work is ongoing to optimise the method of delivery. This mostly contains alignment work with WP4 to make sure needed functionality (e.g. support for LS Login, object storage) is developed but also entails reacting to changes in the software to keep the deployment method in sync.

SD-Desktop

CSC is providing Sensitive Data Remote Desktop (SD Desktop) for its national sensitive data users. There is however no GPU capacity at the moment. Submitting jobs for the backend HPC cluster is being planned. This environment lets users bring their own software with APTAINER containers via SD Connect data transfer service. Data is accessible via SD Gateway, which decrypts the data and makes it visible as a read only mounted directory. For more information, please consult the User Guide <https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/>.

In Bigpicture, project Beneficiaries may pilot such a virtual Linux service for small scale usage. As the service is integrated into CSC's identity management service CSC user accounts and project is required. SD Desktop was demonstrated in Bigpicture Annual meeting 2023 to preview DICOM images, where access was granted via REMS portal. User authenticates with multi factor authentication to get access to the remote desktop web portal and user authenticates with LS AAI to get the token to access data.

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As per the DoA, Bigpicture will enable indirect access to datasets, and both indirect and direct on-platform access to AI algorithms. Bigpicture has not started major work to address these usage patterns yet. Such development can commence once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; Task forces section in D2.08), and adopts an initial standard for metadata on indirectly accessible datasets (cf Metadata task force; Task forces section in D2.08). It is expected that the project will base such services on grand-challenge.org technologies, previously described in D2.03 - Report on private execution model implementation in pilot environment, and in D2.05 - Report on pilot operations. It is not clear yet whether Bigpicture will need the functionality of the entire grand-challenge.org application service available in full or just in part, but wp2 has carried out preliminary investigations of what components may be reusable in the Bigpicture infrastructure. This is not seen as an urgent priority, as it is not immediately intended for use in data submission nor as a primary tool for direct access to AI models or datasets. This will be revisited once a first use case presents itself.

On-demand AI inference on Archive data

Secure processing environment is also needed to execute the selected AI inference models, which is planned to be done using a service that runs the AI model portfolio in the Private Inference Execution Sandbox against all contributed datasets, to produce metadata that is used by the Discovery service, to enable morphological data-mining. This activity with design and piloting shall be done later in the project together with wp3, specifically the discovery service reference group described in the requirement dialogue section of D2.08 - Report on status of operational services implementation. It will require a process to select the model, the platform to execute those, enhancing the metadata model to store the results and possibly adjust the discovery service. Therefore use cases with the users who will utilise the data will be analysed carefully. One unknown factor is the computing resource requirements.

Security review

As part of Task 2.7 - Regular security review, wp2 carries out annual security review of components where changes have been made, and penetration testing of the integrated system in collaboration with independent external cyber security expertise. This is a continuation of the work carried out in Task 2.4 - Security review of pilot systems, and is structured similarly.

The scope of the review included data submission interface implemented in Sweden, data access process and gateway in SD Desktop of CSC, Cytomine pilot instance at UU, discovery web portal with pilot implementation and a test dataset.

The work was conducted in December 2022 - April 2023. CSC made a national procurement process, which was won by cybersecurity company Netox Oy. The budget and timeline was for this yearly work. The final report from the review was delivered to CSC and UU in April 2023. There was also a summary report, which was made available to the Bigpicture consortium. The parts of the report pertinent to application services developed by beneficiaries in other work packages were shared in full with these beneficiaries.

Next round of regular security review is planned to occur in 2024. The exact timing will be optimised to include significant development outcomes.

During spring 2023 auditing strategies were also discussed. As per the DoA, certificates of compliance against a generally accepted data security audit standard (such as ISO 27001 or equivalent national standards) will be requested on a bi-annual basis. This has been refined by wp2+5 to mean that the project will aim to ISO27k certify appropriate services by Apr 2024. Bigpicture Services are not possible to audit as a one service, since they are distributed on several large organisations. Due to the size of these organisations, the scope of an external audit might be limited, or alternatively, be replaced or complemented with Bigpicture-internal audits. Likewise, it is not expected to be in Bigpicture interest to seek certification for all platform services exhaustively, especially considering that substantial feature development efforts are expected to be required in order to support future usage patterns such as in indirect access.

Results

Most of the platform services are described in D2.08 - Report on status of operational services implementation, whereas the focus of this report is services for on-platform data use, which are described in separate sections below.

Concepts

A private inference execution environment is a service for the users, ensuring that the users can work and collaborate selectively and in private, and are only given access to data that they are entitled to. The concepts and services were previously described in D2.03 - Report on private execution model implementation in pilot environment. This environment is used as a basis for development of a private inference execution model that will enable indirect access to datasets or algorithms. This model has been further delineated in D4.05 - Technical description of the application programming interface for integration of AI algorithms in the Bigpicture infrastructure. However, Bigpicture has not yet started developing concrete use cases for indirect access to datasets and algorithms, and thus, the private inference execution environment currently only has limited support for these usage patterns.

The Bigpicture repository is providing Cytomine-server-as-a-service and SD-Desktop as services for direct access to datasets and algorithms, thus allowing users to work collaboratively and in private to analyse and enrich data that is under their own control. WP2 has investigated how to integrate the grand-challenge.org platform into the Bigpicture private inference execution environment, either whole or in parts, as further services offered to support both direct and indirect access to datasets and algorithms. These services are described in further detail in sections below.

The private inference execution model is also anticipated to be useful for taking major steps toward the vision of morphological data mining, as an anticipated late Bigpicture project output previously described in D2.03 - Report on private execution model implementation in pilot environment. This topic will be addressed when concrete demonstrators for this functionality have been produced in wp3+4 and approved for service piloting by the discovery service reference group described in the requirement dialogue section of D2.08. We anticipate that this functionality will require several processes as well as substantial processing accessing of data in the repository in order to execute the selected AI algorithms and to store the outcome. In Petascale, this is expected to be a heavy and time consuming process.

Privacy parameters of the private inference execution model

A guiding principle is that a service should not have more access than absolutely necessary. This is applied from the infrastructure layer and up. All services are by default isolated and then ports and networks are opened as needed, database passwords are application specific. We also isolate users from one another.

For interactive sessions, we have the option of deploying user specific infrastructure in cases where we are not convinced that the service is not isolated or tested enough. Non-interactive sessions will have well defined APIs with the type of data that can be extracted.

CSC is operating sensitive data processing environment on top of it is OpenStack cloud system designed for sensitive data processing. For SD Desktop there is a specific environment with allocated processor cores, RAM and storage capacity. On top of that is running the SD Desktop service described below.

Data repository consisting of software (middleware) and storage system is a different system. There is a high bandwidth connection for accessing the data, but the network latencies and decryption will be slower compared to data on a local disk. For some use cases using a workstorage may thus be needed.

Services

As per the DoA, wp2 provides services for on-platform data use. Some, like SD Desktop, are based on services in long-term production operation at the wp2 infrastructure service hosting partners. Others are application services developed by wp4, such as Cytomine, and hosted in the wp2 private execution environment that is provided by the wp2 infrastructure service hosting partners. The current status of these on-platform services is reported in separate sections below.

Different application services provide different functionalities, and operate under different security models and are differently able to make use of platform security measures, making them differently suitable for use with data with different usage constraints. For example, a data contributor can make the assessment that a given service is perfectly fine to use with those of their contributed datasets that contain anonymised data, while at the same time be unsuitable for use with those of their datasets that contain personal data. In the end, the decision on what constitutes reasonable data protection can only be made by the contributor, who has the necessary knowledge of the contents, and the ethical and legal context of the data. These decisions must be made on a case-by-case basis. However, data contributors will likely be able to make these assessments for their contributed datasets on a service-by-service level. WP3 is working to develop terms of use to reflect these assessments (cf Metadata task force; Task forces section in D2.08).

Cytomine

As per the DoA, Cytomine is intended as the main user frontend interface to Bigpicture, to operate on top of platform backend interfaces provided by wp2. Cytomine is an application service developed by wp4, and is hosted in the private execution environment provided by wp2. The intention is that Cytomine will provide a range of functionalities including data search, submission of datasets, launching AI image analyses, visualising and interacting with images, downloading images, and for annotation. Some of these functionalities are in place, and some are under development by wp4.

Currently, wp2 can provide Bigpicture beneficiaries with private on-platform Cytomine servers as-a-service, on request. The intention is that such private Cytomine-server-as-a-service instances will be made available to users in platform user groups (which are individually managed by each user organisation, as described in the User authentication and authorisation section in D2.08) where they will be able to work with datasets that they have approved direct access to (as described in the Entitlement management section in D2.08) as well as own uploaded data. This scenario is illustrated in Fig. 1, and will become possible once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; Task forces section in D2.08), and once support for Life Science AAI login has been implemented in Cytomine by wp4 as per the DoA. Until such a time, the Cytomine native account management system is used, and instances must be pre-populated with copies of all datasets to be used in this instance. This is of course demanding in terms of storage space requirements, and does not scale well to a situation where multiple instances are operated in parallel, for groups working with multiple (copies of the same?) large datasets. It also creates challenges in entitlement management, for example in effecting access revocations, which in this scenario will not be effective immediately on data controller revocation in REMS, but will require manual intervention by the users in the platform user group to actually remove the data that they no longer should have access to themselves.

These scalability issues and entitlement management issues are expected to be obviated once Cytomine support for working against repository data directly using for Life Science AAI authenticated and authorised object storage has been implemented by wp4 as per the DoA. The project may decide to develop a dedicated web service for making requests for private Cytomine-server-as-a-service instances. If so, then this will become possible once the project adopts its upcoming legal framework for data sharing (cf GDPR task force; Task forces section in D2.08), at which time wp2 can take on such development tasks, within available resources and according to project priorities (cf the Requirement dialogue and Decision making sections in D2.08). Until such a time, to enable pilot use for service development purposes, the project uses an interim solution where data users make such requests directly to the service operating beneficiaries, detailing exactly which individuals (affiliation, name, email) that the instance is intended for, and which datasets should be made available in this instance, which are then matched against the corresponding existing explicit access grants communicated to the

service operating beneficiaries in written instruction by the data contributing organisations (as described in the Entitlement management section in D2.08) before the instance is created and populated with data. The request should also define what exact IP ranges that the service instance should be made reachable from. The requestor is made administrator of the instance, and can carry out account management on the instance as needed.

As described in the Data download section in D2.08, Cytomine provides support for downloading images. This download functionality however does not support the recipient specific encryption of downloaded data that the sda-cli download functionality provides.

As alluded to in the Services for on-platform data use section in D2.08, data contributors will have to exercise their own judgement when deciding what level of security is needed for their datasets.

Recently, a new release of Cytomine was made available to the consortium, which introduces support for the Bigpicture data format (DICOM, xml), thus making it possible to view and work with Bigpicture WSI in Cytomine. This new version also introduces a new refactored version of the Cytomine core. The standard way of deploying instances of Cytomine is now via docker compose. Previously, wp2 developed ways to make it easier to deploy and manage parallel instances of Cytomine consistently, using infrastructure-as-code, i.e. using Helm charts, in a secure Kubernetes environment. WP2 has now made the same effort for the new release and made this new functionality available to Bigpicture platform users. The Helm charts have been made available in an open source software repository¹ and shared with Cytomine developers, for inclusion by default as a deployment option for all Cytomine users in future releases.

SD Desktop

SD Desktop is a secure remote desktop service developed by CSC for its national usage for research projects using sensitive data. Jobs can be run within a virtual machine, which is enough for example viewing the images or running some non-AI jobs. There is a batch job submission planned for a scalable backend. As SD Desktop is a browser based secure remote desktop system, it is not optimal for providing a high-performant user experience when running other browser-based applications like Cytomine inside the remote desktop containment. The SD Desktop system is described in D2.03 - Report on private execution model implementation in pilot environment, and in D2.05 - Report on pilot operations.

To get an access, CSC user account and project is created via CSC's processes as there is a project needed for the SD Desktop and for the Object Storage service for data stage-in and out. Data transfer will be done with SD Connect tool, which has web and command line interfaces. Essential is that the data is encrypted. SD Gateway tool is mounting the user's own object storage project and/or the granted datasets. This is made available for user who has authenticated with LS AAI. After login to SD Desktop, the user can start a pre-built computing environment (Linux OS). User can bring applications via containers with SD Connect service.

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WP2 currently has verified that it can deploy the grand-challenge.org application service inside the private execution environment, in such a way that it can be provided to beneficiaries in the same manner as the current Cytomine-server-as-a-service, using the same process, and with the same limitations. WP2 has also adapted the non-restricted parts of grand-challenge.org for more resource effective deployments using kubernetes. The software does not currently support Life Science Login and alignment work with WP4 for needed functionality is ongoing.

¹ <https://github.com/NBISweden/cytomine-bp-helm>

Security review

The external security review work described in the Security review section in Methods above were evaluated and addressed in wp2 systems and services. The findings were communicated to the relevant parties and the summary report from the reviewer was stored in the Bigpicture document management platform. The next evaluation is due in 2024.

Conclusion

This report provides a description of the state of the operational system at the time when the first real non-clinical data submissions are being prepared and submitted. Services have now reached a high degree of technical readiness to open up for wide use, pending project adoption of upcoming legal framework for data sharing and critical metadata standards.

Bigpicture is actively working on the direct access suitable security processing environment. Already now SD Desktop, which is integrated to REMS, can be piloted. Cytomine instances are provided as well, yet there is some manual work needed for authorised data interfaces. Yearly penetration testing was done for the current environment by an external cybersecurity company. For indirect access there is planning work being carried out together with grand-challenge.org platform. This access model is not yet needed. As such Bigpicture now provides a diverse set of data access options for several use cases, which will be optimised upon use by future users.